

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: THE FUTURE FOR DIABETES CARE

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ABSTRACT. Artificial intelligence (AI) is a fast-growing field and its applications to diabetes, a global pandemic, can reform the approach to diagnosis and management of this chronic condition. Principles of machine learning have been used to build algorithms to support predictive models for the risk of developing diabetes or its consequent complications. Digital therapeutics have proven to be an established intervention for lifestyle therapy in the management of diabetes. Patients are increasingly being empowered for self-management of diabetes, and both patients and health care professionals are benefitting from clinical decision support. AI allows a continuous and burden-free remote monitoring of the patient's symptoms and biomarkers. Further, social media and online communities enhance patient engagement in diabetes care. Technical advances have helped to optimize resource use in diabetes. Together, these intelligent technical reforms have produced better glycemic control with reductions in fasting and postprandial glucose levels, glucose excursions, and glycosylated hemoglobin. AI will introduce a paradigm shift in diabetes care from conventional management strategies to building targeted data-driven precision care.

KEYWORDS: Artificial intelligence (AI); Diabetes; Machine learning; Management; Prediction

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes, a chronic metabolic condition, is a global health care burden. According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), 463 million people between ages 20 and 79 years have diabetes, and 374 million have impaired glucose tolerance.¹ By the year 2045, 693 million people are likely to have diabetes.² While 8.8% of the world population was reported to have diabetes in 2017, the numbers are projected to rise to 10% by 2045.³ Diabetes is associated with various complications and a significant morbidity and mortality.⁴ It is important to intervene not only to treat but also to prevent and make a timely detection of diabetes. Management of diabetes is challenging because 1 of 2 adults with diabetes are undiagnosed, yet 10% of global health expenditure (US\$760 billion) are spent on diabetes.¹ Artificial intelligence (AI) finds widespread use in four key areas in diabetes care, including automated retinal screening, clinical decision support, predictive population risk stratification, and patient self-management tools.^{5,6} The purpose of this review is to provide an overview of the scope and utility of AI in the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of diabetes.

Techniques

Several AI-based techniques have been applied in diabetes care. With the advent of AI, the diagnosis of diabetes has evolved beyond a few measurements of blood glucose levels and glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c). Case-based reasoning (CBR). CBR, an AI technique to solve new problems based on learning from similar past encounters, is being extensively used in diabetes management.^{17,18} The 4 Diabetes Support System is an example of CBR that has been used in diabetes care. The system aims to automatically detect problems in control of blood glucose, propose solutions to the detected problems, and remember the effective and ineffective solutions for individual patients. CBR has been used to optimize and individualize

insulin therapy for various meal situations in diabetes. Machine learning and deep learning. Several machine learning processes have been used to build digital support in diabetes care. These include support vector machine, artificial neural network, naïve Bayes, decision tree, random forest, classification and regression trees, and k-nearest neighbor. Machine learning has been applied to create automated screening for blood glucose variability.¹⁷ Principles of machine learning, including feature selection techniques (eg, random forest, logistic regression, mutual information, principal component analysis, analysis of variance, and Fisher discriminant ratio), outlier removal techniques, cross-validation protocols, and classifiers (eg, linear discriminant analysis, quadratic discriminant analysis, naïve Bayes, Gaussian process classification, support vector machine, artificial neural network, Adaboost, logistic regression, decision tree, and random forest) have been used to accurately stratify the risk of diabetes and identify patients with diabetes and controls). Machine learning programs can identify people at high risk for diabetes based on genetic and metabolic factors. Artificial neural networks. Neural networks have been created to link and analyze disparate information and build personalized solutions. Neural network methodology has found particular and vast applications in diabetes diagnosis. Intelligent algorithms have been constructed to study the impact of various factors on glycemic indices. Others. Other techniques like support vector regression (SVR) have been applied to diabetes care. Support vector regression has been used to build a hypoglycemia predictor. This creates an alert for preventive intervention when patients have alarmingly low levels of blood glucose.¹⁷ Together, these technologies find wide application in diabetes care.

APPLICATIONS

Automated retinal screening. Deep learning algorithms have been developed to automate the diagnosis of diabetic retinopathy. AI-based screening of retina is a feasible, accurate, and well-accepted method for the detection and monitoring of diabetic retinopathy. A high sensitivity and specificity of 92.3% and 93.7%, respectively, have been reported for automated screening of the retina. Patient satisfaction for automated screening is also high with 96% patients reported as being satisfied or very satisfied with this method.²³ Convolutional neural networks (CNN) have been trained on limited data sets to generate lesion-specific probability maps for hemorrhages, microaneurysms, exudates, neovascularization, and normal appearance in the retina.

Clinical decision support. Supervised machine learning based clinical decision support tools have been developed to predict short- and long-term HbA1c response after insulin initiation in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. These tools also help to identify clinical variables that can influence a patient's HbA1c response. The elastic net regularization-based generalized linear model based on baseline HbA1c and estimated glomerular filtration rate is reported to reliably predict the HbA1c response after insulin initiation. Areas under the curve (AUC) of 0.80 (95% confidence interval [CI] 0.78–0.83) and 0.81 (95% CI 0.79–0.84), respectively, are reported for short- and long-term HbA1c response. Machine learning has been used to develop an intuitive approach for customizing interventions in medication adherence and predicting the risk of hospitalization in diabetes. In a retrospective cohort study (n = 33,130), machine learning yielded adherence thresholds of 46% to 94% as most discriminating for risk of all-cause hospitalization. This study confirmed the variability of predictive adherence thresholds according to patient characteristics and complexity of

medications. Predictive population risk stratification. Healthcare recommendation system (HRS) using machine learning helped to predict the risk for a disease, including diabetes, by analyzing patient's lifestyle, physical health factors, mental health factors, and their social network activities. Data from 68,994 healthy people and patients with diabetes has been used as a training data set for using decision tree, random forest, and neural networks to predict diabetes with high accuracy (accuracy = 0.8084 with all attributes).²⁷ Predictive models have been built to leverage big data analytics for building estimates of possibility of development of complications in patients with diabetes. Many such models have been developed to predict the development of both long-term (eg, retinal, cardiovascular, and renal) and short-term (ie, hypoglycemia) complications of diabetes. Trained to interpret images of feet, mobile apps have been introduced to follow-up with patients with diabetes for development of diabetic foot ulcers.²⁹ Machine learning has been used to develop decision tree models for prediction of development of type 2 diabetes mellitus in pregnant women with gestational diabetes. The discriminative power of this prediction method was 83.0% in the training set and 76.9% in an independent testing set, making it superior to conventional monitoring of fasting glucose levels.

SUMMARY

AI is attracting attention for the management of diabetes. AI enables us to rethink diabetes and redefine the strategies for prevention and management of diabetes. AI supports the development of prediction models to estimate the risk of diabetes and its related complications. This will help to bring in an element of personalized care in the management of diabetes. Patients are now being empowered to manage their own health and physicians can provide a timely and targeted intervention through technical platforms. These advances save time and cost because data can be collected remotely and virtual management is replacing the routine visits to a clinic. AI has introduced a quantum change in diabetes care and will continue to evolve. Going further, broader experience generated from the continuous use of AI will help to standardize the functionality and utility in diabetes care.

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